

panicle BL. Varieties scored higher than 6 are vulnerable to BL and damage could be high. Cultivation of many cultivars in rank 9 was discontinued because of severe outbreak of BL. Yet several late-

maturing varieties with good grain quality favored by Koreans are widely grown in the southern plain of Korea with intensive applications of chemicals for BL control. On these varieties, panicle

BL is less severe than leaf BL.

The ranking can be applied to other varieties when no historical quantitative disease data are available. □

Varietal reaction to tungro (RTV) with change in leafhopper "virulence"

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Green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* populations were periodically collected at Koronadal, South Cotabato; Maligaya, Nueva Ecija; and Los Baños (IRRI Experimental Farm), Laguna, in the Philippines in 1986-88 and reared on TN1 plants in cages in an insect-proof greenhouse. First or second generation adults that had fed on RTV-infected plants were allowed to feed 1 d on test seedlings. GLH feeding behavior was monitored by the color reaction of honeydew excreted by GLH on bromocresol-treated filter paper disks: blue color (basic reaction) indicates phloem feeding and brown or orange color (acidic reaction) indicates xylem feeding. At 3 wk after the feeding, seedlings were indexed by latex serology for the presence of rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical (RTSV) viruses.

GLH populations collected thrice at Koronadal had similar transmission efficiency and feeding behavior on each test cultivar. GLH populations collected thrice at Maligaya were also similar. All these populations transmitted RTBV and RTSV together (RTBV + RTSV) at high efficiency and fed mainly from both phloem and xylem on IR54.

Six populations collected at Los Baños varied in their transmission efficiencies and feeding behavior, especially on IR54. Populations collected prior to Apr 1987 transmitted mostly RTBV alone and fed mainly from xylem on IR54. Populations collected after Aug 1987 efficiently transmitted RTBV + RTSV, and fed predominantly' from both phloem and

Area of acidic and basic honeydew spots (a), percentage of area of basic honeydew spots (b) excreted by 6 GLH collections from IRRI farm, Los Baños, Philippines, Aug 1986-Jan 1988, during a 22-h inoculation feeding, and transmission of RTBV and RTSV to 6 rice cultivars (c). IRRI, 1988.

RTBV and RTSV incidence^a in 14 rice cultivars in demonstration plots at IRRI, 1986 and 1988 DS.^b

Cultivar	1986 dry season			1988 dry season				
	Plants tested (no.)	Plants (%) with			Plants tested (no.)	Plants (%) with		
		RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV		RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
IR8	—	—	—	—	36	56	14	19
IR22	36	87	11	2	—	—	—	—
IR26	36	0	59	0	36	0	31	0
IR30	36	0	41	0	36	0	25	0
IR36	36	67	7	15	36	11	0	75
IR42	36	70	12	10	36	61	0	36
IR54	36	1	3	19	56	71	11	16
IR58	36	0	0	9	36	3	0	33
IR64	50 ^c	0	6	12	70	66	4	23
Gam Pai 30-12-15	90 ^d	0	1	9	34	80	15	0
Sigadis	—	50	22	7	34	38	9	24
Peta	90 ^d	2	12	7	36	78	8	6
TN1	36	83	13	2	—	—	—	—

^aPlants were indexed by latex serology. ^bDashes indicate not tested. ^cTested in 1985 WS. ^dTested in 1985 DS.

xylem on IR54 and IR64 (see figure). Additional measurements Jan-Feb 1988 confirmed this. The shift in feeding

behavior on IR54 and IR64 of the Los Baños population from predominant xylem feeding to phloem and xylem

feeding could be the major reason for the shift in virus transmission efficiency.

At Los Baños, RTV incidence in IR54, IR64, and some other cultivars having Gam Pai 30-12-15 in their parentage was very low before the 1986

wet season (WS) and very high from 1987 dry season (DS) onward. RTBV + RTSV incidence on IR54 and IR64 was very low in 1986, but very high in 1988 (see table). Gam Pai 30-12-15 also had high incidence of RTBV + RTSV in

1988. These results indicate the breakdown of IR54 and IR64 resistance to RTV in Los Baños in 1987 DS was due to a shift in GLH virulence. RTBV + RTSV incidence on IR36 was high in 1986, but low in 1988 (see table). □

Resistance to bacterial leaf streak (BLS) in hybrid rice and parental lines

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Five rice hybrids from IRRI and their male sterile (A) and restorer (R) lines were evaluated against two isolates of BLS in the greenhouse. Pregerminated seeds were grown in plastic trays, three rows in a tray, one for each F₁, A, and R lines.

Isolates 93 and 335 of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola* were used to spray-inoculate the test plants at 21 and 30 d after sowing (DAS). The bacterial suspension was adjusted to 10⁹ cells/ml. Scoring was done 10 and 15 d after inoculation (DAI) using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES), based on leaf area infection.

Reactions of different A and R lines and F₁ to BLS. IRRI, 1988.

Hybrid	Reaction ^a					
	Isolate 93			Isolate 335		
	A	R	F ₁	A	R	F ₁
IR46830A/IR50	7.2	4.9	7.7	2.5	2.2	3.8
	4.0	3.7	4.4	6.0	3.7	5.1
IR46830A/IR9761-19-1	8.0	8.9	8.5	5.2	6.1	4.9
	4.6	5.3	6.3	7.4	6.5	6.8
IR54752A/IR54	8.8	7.5	7.9	3.4	0.3	2.5
	3.8	2.4	3.2	5.0	3.7	5.7
IR54752A/IR19392-211-1	8.7	8.7	8.9	3.1	1.8	2.0
	3.1	4.8	4.3	5.2	6.0	6.3
Zhongshan 97A/Milyang 54	8.4		2.1	3.7		0.0
	6.2	0	2.0	7.5	0	2.7

^aScores are averages at 10 DAI on plants inoculated at 21 DAS (first row in each set), and 30 DAS (second row). 0-3 = resistant, 3.1-4.9 = moderately resistant, 5-9 = susceptible.

Of the five hybrids, Zhongshan 97A/ Milyang 54 was resistant to the two isolates in both inoculation stages (see table). IR46830A and IR54752A became moderately resistant when inoculated with isolate 93 at 30 DAS.

The two parental lines with moderate resistance produced rice hybrids with moderate resistance. The R line contributed resistance in F₁ for the A line-susceptible and R line-resistant combination. □

Sieve tube number in tungro (RTV)-infected rice plants

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To study the effect of RTV infection on phloem tissues, we collected leaves from healthy and RTV-infected rice plants. Cross sections of leaves of the same age were dipped in a saturated solution of phloroglucinol in 18% hydrochloric acid. The phloem cells per microscopic field were counted.

We found no necrosis of phloem cells in infected leaves. However, the mean number of sieve tubes was 123 in healthy leaves, compared to 73 in diseased leaves. We conclude that RTV reduced sieve tubes 41%. □

Simplification of sampling method for assessing bacterial blight (BB) severity

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This study attempted to simplify methods to assess BB (*Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*) severity. Rice variety RD9 was transplanted into 5 × 5 m² plots at Pathum Thani Rice Research Center, Thailand, during DS 1987. Disease was induced by inoculation in several levels on border rows of seven treatments with two replications each.

Severity was assessed 5 times at 49 d after transplanting (DT), 55 DT, 62 DT, 69 DT, and 76 DT, on 8 hills per plot. Leaf area damage on each of the top three leaves of each tiller (LAD1, LAD2, and LAD3) as well as whole hill damage (VLAD) were visually assessed and expressed in percent. The average leaf area damage of leaves 1-3 (ALAD) and disease incidence for each leaf position (IL1, IL2, IL3, and ILT) were calculated.

At maximum tillering (49 DT) and booting (55 DT) severity on the third leaf (LAD3) was highly correlated with average severity on the whole hill (ALAD) (see table). At flowering (62 DT), close correlations between average severity on a hill and severity on second or third leaves (LAD2 and LAD3) were found. At milk (69 DT) and dough